

Assigning Parole

April 28, 2026

1 Description

A district court, CourtOnYourDistrict, determines prison sentences based on the risk of re-offending, with longer sentences for prisoners at high risk of re-offending.

1) **CourtOnYourDistrict relies on employees to assess a prisoner's risk of re-offending.**

- a) Imagine you are a prisoner of CourtOnYourDistrict. How acceptable do you find it when an employee assesses the risk of re-offending?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- b) Please describe a situation where using employees would be beneficial for assessing the risk of re-offending.
- c) Please describe a situation where using employees would be harmful for assessing the risk of re-offending.

An organization, TechForLegal collects data on wealthy prisoners, including the nature of their offenses, their criminal history, their mental health, their employability, behavioral changes, and parole officer recommendations.

TechForLegal uses the collected data to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict whether a prisoner will re-offend.

2) **Instead of employees, the CourtOnYourDistrict now relies on TechForLegal's AI to assess a prisoner's risk of re-offending.**

- a) Imagine you are a prisoner of CourtOnYourDistrict. How acceptable do you find it when an AI assesses the risk of re-offending?
 - i) completely unacceptable

- ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be beneficial for assessing the risk of re-offending.
 - Please describe a situation where using the AI would be harmful for assessing the risk of re-offending.

3) **Consider that CourtOnYourDistrict relies on TechForLegal’s AI to assess a prisoner’s risk of re-offending and determine their prison sentences. TechForLegal identified an issue with its AI where it offers shorter prison sentence to brunettes over non-brunettes, even if they have a high risk. To address this, TechForLegal modifies the AI to mitigate the issue.**

- Please describe how ‘the AI modification’ could be beneficial for everyone.

Modifying the AI has some side effects, which are described as different scenarios in parts (a), (b), (c) and (d). Please indicate your preference for the following scenarios:

- a) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that it incorrectly predicts longer prison sentence for low risk prisoners. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still provide correct prison sentences for low risk prisoners. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLegal to choose?**
 - i) The AI strongly favors brunettes; otherwise, it provides the correct prison sentences.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it provides slightly incorrect prison sentences.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it provides moderately incorrect prison sentences.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it provides highly incorrect prison sentences
 - Give an example of potential issues if TechForLegal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- b) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that CourtOnYourDistrict can learn whether a prisoner is wealthy by identifying if they were part of TechForLegal’s data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still prevent CourtOnYourDistrict from identifying a prisoner is wealthy. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLegal to choose?**

- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal whether the applicant is wealthy.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal whether the applicant is wealthy.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal whether the applicant is wealthy.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal whether the applicant is wealthy.
 - Give an example of potential issues if TechForLegal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- c) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that CourtOnYourDistrict can now determine the number of women in TechForLegal’s data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still protect the information about the number of women. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLegal to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - Give an example of potential issues if TechForLegal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- d) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that CourtOnYourDistrict’s employees could exploit the AI to disadvantage blue-eyed applicants by giving them a longer prison sentence. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and protect the AI from manipulation. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLegal to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it is highly difficult to manipulate.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it is moderately difficult to manipulate.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it is slightly difficult to manipulate.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it is not difficult to manipulate.
 - Give an example of potential issues if TechForLegal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

2 Demographic Information

- 1) What is your gender?
 - Man | Woman | Non-Binary | Prefer not to answer | Self-describe [text input]
- 2) Do you identify as being part of any minority groups?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 3) What age group do you belong to?
 - 18-25 | 26-35 | 36-45 | 46-55 | 56-65 | Prefer not to answer
- 4) What is your highest level of education?
 - Less than a high school degree | High school degree or equivalent [Non-university education beyond high-school (technical college, community college, vocational education) | Some college, no degree | Bachelor's or Associate's degree | Master's degree | Doctoral degree | Prefer not to answer
- 5) Are you a practitioner (researcher, working professional) in Machine Learning?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 6) Please provide your Prolific ID, this is important to get the compensation.